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Pumped seawater tanks for risk mitigation of marine renewable energy devices

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Abstract

Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) is a fast-growing industry in the clean energy and blue economy space as innovators look to reduce or remove emissions from carbon-based energy generation. Some of the greatest challenges faced by MRE devices include biofouling and corrosion in the ocean environment. Currently, it is cost prohibitive to test these devices in situ due to permitting, ship chartering, and cost of prototypes. It can take years to develop and build these prototypes while securing funding for open-water testing. Once deployed, premature device failure can be a very costly and time-consuming issue. A common way to test MRE components is with a wave or tow tank, but these are generally chlorinated, freshwater tanks devoid of biofouling-causing marine life.

Triton Systems, Inc. is developing a small-scale wave energy converter to provide power (100-500 Watts) to instrumentation buoys; this WEC is a tail-tube style device with a piston inside a cylinder and a depth tube that extends beneath the buoy. Early in the development process, Triton identified that the greatest risk to system operation was biofouling of the inside of the piston cylinder and depth tube. While preparing for wave tank testing and open water deployments, Triton looked to mitigate the risk of premature device failure.

Through the Department of Energy's Testing Expertise and Access for Marine Energy Research (TEAMER), Triton was awarded "Biofouling Analysis for Wave Energy Piston Design," a project in collaboration with the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL). A half-scaled Triton WEC prototype was installed in a tank at the PNNL-Sequim campus, which pumped raw sea water from the local bay while being inside a laboratory building, allowing for controlled testing over four months.

During this testing, several key findings were identified, including the performance of a thermoset epoxy piston cylinder against biofouling, effects of diurnal temperature cycle on metal piston expansion and seal effectiveness, and corrosion of dissimilar metals. As a result, Triton was able to make changes to the wave energy converter design before these issues could have negative impacts on wave tank and open water tests.

This paper will explore the design of experiments, test setup, and results from this TEAMER project. A case will be made that use of raw pumped seawater tanks provide a useful risk mitigation step during the development of marine renewable energy devices. The benefits of industry and national laboratory collaboration will also be highlighted.

Keywords: wave energy; risk mitigation; marine renewable energy

1. Short Paper

1.1. Introduction

Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) is a fast-growing industry in the clean energy and blue economy space as innovators look to reduce or remove emissions from carbon-based energy generation. Some of the greatest challenges faced by MRE devices include biofouling and corrosion in the ocean environment. Currently, it is cost prohibitive to test these devices *in situ* due to permitting, ship chartering, and cost of prototypes. It can take years to develop and build these prototypes while securing funding for open-water testing. Once deployed, premature device failure can be a very costly and time-consuming issue. A common way to test MRE components is with a wave or tow tank, but these are generally chlorinated, freshwater tanks devoid of biofouling-causing marine life.

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1.2. TEAMER

Through the Department of Energy's Testing Expertise and Access for Marine Energy Research (TEAMER), Triton was awarded "Biofouling Analysis for Wave Energy Piston Design." This project was developed in collaboration with the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL), specifically PNNL-Sequim. A half-scaled Triton WEC prototype was installed in a tank at the PNNL-Sequim campus, which pumped raw sea water from the local bay while being inside a laboratory building, allowing for controlled testing over four months.

1.2.1. Technical Assistance Objectives

Triton wanted to test the performance of the seal and component materials within the Power Take-Off (PTO) assembly, specifically with regards to biofouling. Biofouling was identified as one of the most difficult aspects to test, as it often requires a prolonged deployment *in situ*, which is expensive and time consuming.

Through TEAMER, Triton requested technical support for the testing of a half-scale PTO prototype to study the effects of biofouling. This testing took place within controlled biofouling tanks at PNNL, which removed the excessive costs and complexity of open water tests for biofouling.

The study focused on continuous monitoring and periodic evaluation of the piston assembly to characterize the growth of biofouling. Two prototype test articles were compared, one with a biofouling mitigation (wiper) seal, and one without. This evaluation was done through visual inspection and other quantitative methods, such as weighing the assembly to calculate added biofouling weight. Caliper measurements were taken of the inside surface. In-depth biofouling analysis was performed on material coupons at the conclusion of the effort. At the end of the test period, the prototype was deconstructed, and all parts analyzed for corrosion and biofouling. An integrated load cell monitored the resistance experienced by the piston.

1.2.2. Test Facility, Equipment, and Technical Expertise

Testing was conducted at PNNL-Sequim's wet laboratory space. The devices under test were mounted to and operated in a seawater flow-through tank (Fig.1) 1.5 m in diameter and 0.91 m deep. Unfiltered seawater from Sequim Bay was pumped into and drained from the tank at a fixed rate to ensure circulation. In these tanks, growth of marine organisms is uncontrolled and entirely dependent on the natural biota within the water, which varies with season and other exogenous conditions in the bay.

Fig. 1. (a) Empty Wet Lab flow-through tank; (b) active biofouling experiment.

PNNL-Sequim staff expertise encompasses the fields of biology, chemistry and engineering; with specialization in biofouling and corrosion, electrical and mechanical engineering, microscopy, and applied marine technology.

1.2.3. Test Articles

Triton developed the concept of a biofouling mitigation seal as part of the piston sealing assembly. This mitigation seal has the purpose of preventing the formation of a biofilm on the inside of the piston cylinder. It was hypothesized that the prevention of a biofilm would reduce the amount of macro-biofouling that could occur in the piston assembly. The mitigation seal might also reduce the wear on the main dynamic seal, helping to maintain smooth operation and watertightness. The cylinder is made from a thermoset composite epoxy, which is resistant to corrosion. However, no studies have researched the material's performance with biofouling.

Triton provided PNNL with two test articles that mimicked the conceptual design of the wave energy converter. One article had a wiper seal in the configuration shown in Fig. 2; the other article was a control with no wiper seal. A linear actuator was pre-programmed with a sinusoidal wave pattern to simulate wave motion. A load cell was included between the linear actuator and the piston to monitor forces during testing. These two devices were then placed in the biofouling tank for the testing campaigns (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. (a) sealing configuration; (b) test articles installed in biofouling tank

1.3. Results

During this testing, several key findings were identified, including the performance of a thermoset epoxy piston cylinder against biofouling, effects of diurnal temperature cycle on metal piston expansion and seal effectiveness, and corrosion of dissimilar metals.

1.3.1. Early Failure

Over the initial two-weeks of testing, load cell force increased steadily until the pistons were jammed in the Device Under Test. In response, the researchers at PNNL conducted a thorough investigation. After disassembling the device, the wearbands were identified as the problem source (Fig. 3). The wearbands contained a previously undisclosed bronze-powder additive, which galvanically corroded when in contact with salt water and aluminum.

Fig. 3. (a) Galvanic corrosion on aluminum piston; (b) Corrosion on wearband

1.3.2. Seal Performance

The assembly with the wiper seal showed higher forces throughout the test (Fig. 4). Qualitative observations suggested there was less biofouling under the stroke with the wiper, but this was not statistically confirmed with data.

Fig. 4. Piston load cell force over time; Wiper (blue) vs Control (orange)

1.3.3. Temperature

During testing, the researchers noticed that load cell forces fluctuated daily in a repeatable pattern. The forces were plotted against the temperature of water in Sequim Bay, where the raw seawater was sourced. These results are shown

in Fig. 5. It was determined that the aluminum pistons were expanding with warmer water temperatures, leading to higher normal forces against the seals and therefore higher friction forces.

Fig. 5. RMS-filtered load cell force and tank water temperature

1.4. Conclusions

The researchers at the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory compiled the findings above, performed initial analyses, and collaborated with Triton to understand the processes and causes behind these results. Triton was then able to make changes to the wave energy converter design before these issues could have negative impacts on pending wave tank and open water tests.

The early failure of the composite wearbands allowed Triton to select an alternative material that was not reactive with seawater. Triton used the load cell and temperature data to investigate other sealing methods that do not exert high normal forces with changing water temperatures. Results from biofouling and corrosion investigations allowed for improvements in material selection and biofouling mitigation.

Triton was only able to perform this risk mitigation activity because of PNNL's facility capabilities and funding from TEAMER. These tests would be too expensive to conduct in traditional ocean environments with Triton's existing government grants. In the worst-case scenario, proceeding to the scheduled full-scale deployments with the initial design would have led to pre-mature failure and loss of tens of thousands of dollars for emergency retrieval and repairs, as well as a delay in technical progress.

Based on this experience, the project team believes that expanded access to pumped raw seawater tanks and similar facilities could allow for further risk mitigation activities within the marine renewable energy community. This could enable improved performance and increased chances of success during open-water deployments, leading to an overall improvement in the industry.

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